

DEVELOPMENT OF COLLABORATIVE SKILLS OF STUDENTS BASED ON MULTI-VECTOR PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL APPROACHES IN THE MODERN EDUCATIONAL PROGRAM

Turemuratova Aziza Begibaevna

Assistant, Department of Pedagogy and Psychology,
Karakalpak State University named after Berdakh,
Republic of Karakalpakstan, Uzbekistan

Khojabaeva Maral Davletbayevna

Aytbaeva Sayyora O'mirbek kizi

Orazbaeva Mag'rupa Berdibay kizi

Students of Karakalpak State University named after Berdakh

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13943657>

Abstract. The article provides a comparative analysis of the concepts of electronic, cooperative, collaborative, blended, inverse learning, and raises the question of the legitimacy of classifying them as educational innovations. Particular attention is paid to open distance learning in digital networks. The authors emphasize that, although today the development of computer software allows everyone to receive an education using digital networks, research shows that successful one-on-one learning with a computer is difficult and not possible for everyone.

Keywords: open distance learning in digital networks, cooperative learning, collaborative learning.

INTRODUCTION

Collaboration (1830). From the Latin collaborare (co - together and laborare - to work), cooperation implies working together with someone, participating in the creation of a joint product with the support of one or more employees. The concept of "work, labor together with ..." is appropriate and applicable to a wide range of human groups. Cooperation can be expressed in the form of contribution, participation, joint management, assistance, service, benefits, etc. In cooperation, group members work towards a common goal, but individually, each strives to achieve a specific goal. Two types of activity are carried out in parallel: collective and individual of each of the participants. This requires the organization of work corresponding to the situation of cooperation, when the goals and objectives are common.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Work is accomplished as individual contributions overlap, with continuous adjustments and regroupings. It involves the mutual involvement of people

(subjects) in a coordinated effort to accomplish a single task and/or to jointly solve the same problem. Individual work is difficult to identify because it is fully integrated into the overall activity throughout the process. Responsibility is thus continually shared among all participants whose actions determine the final results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Collaborative learning. Collaborative learning [1] can be seen as a philosophy of interaction and a way of life where people are responsible for their actions, including their learning, and respect the capabilities and contributions of their partners. Collaborative learning “is a way of learning in which the learner learns through interaction with peers” [2]. The educational outcome of the learner’s individual work in constructing his or her knowledge is supported by the activities of the group and team. The learner shares resources with the group, uses group work to learn. The structure of the activity is flexible and open, and the route of exploration and discovery is free. The teacher plays the role of a facilitator in learning, while the group acts as a source of information, motivation, as a means of self-help and mutual support, and as a special place of interaction for collective knowledge construction. In collaborative learning, there is no a priori distribution of roles, as in simple joint (cooperative) work.

Individuals gradually merge with the group, which becomes a single whole and whose potential is greater than the sum of its parts, which often allows for high-quality work. At the same time, there is both individual responsibility for the common cause and the responsibility of the team as a whole. All members of the group maintain close and constant contact, each brings their own action to the group, each can contribute to the work of other members of the group in order to increase productivity and thus join the principle of continuous improvement in the performance of each task and the project as a whole. The interaction of group members is long-term, and it is the coordination of the team that helps in achieving the final goal. For greater coordination between group members, the number of its participants should be no more than five people. Often, when adult learners, sometimes teachers, hear the term collaborative learning, it is automatically associated with the negative context of working in a group, from which they had to suffer in the school environment or in the workplace. They refer to their own, sometimes unpleasant, experiences, which makes them want to abandon the concept of collaboration, which they regard as unrealistic or as an attempt to shift the burden of learning from the teacher to

the students. In open distance learning, we must explain well the benefits of collaborative work and the need to support each of its participants, especially in terms of motivational dynamics, where the external aspect is a necessary variable in building success. This initial concern of some students is worth noting, since it represents an example of misunderstanding of what has become an absolutely indispensable approach to the greatest viability of teaching and learning in digital networks.

Principles. Collaborative learning can be based on the following principles:

- the results of working together lead to mutual understanding, perhaps greater than when working independently;
- oral and written interactions contribute to the best understanding;
- the ability to recognize through lived experience the relationships that exist between social interaction and better mutual understanding;
- some elements of this deep understanding are idiosyncratic and unpredictable;
- participation is voluntary and should provide freedom, but at the same time be strongly supported.

It seems that the collaborative learning mode requires a broader participation of stakeholders. For a group, this ability to develop its human capital is considered by some as a sign of collective intelligence. According to Pierre Levy [3], collective intelligence is a distributed intelligence throughout the world, because no one knows everything, but everyone knows something. Knowledge is present in man, not in some transcendent entity that organizes its ever wider dissemination in society; therefore, a well-organized collective is the main human wealth, which is personally coordinated in real time. Here we must make reference to cyberspace as an instrument of assistance and support for collective intelligence, which allows for large-scale communication, which leads to an effective mobilization of skills [4]. Collective intelligence is nothing more than a theoretical or philosophical concept; it can underlie a new effective and efficient social organization based on skills, knowledge and experience.

Collective intelligence promotes the power of creative potential that exists in each of us, as opposed to isolated, divided and weakened power. For P. Levy, power provides an opportunity, power blocks it, which is why he calls for “destroying hierarchies” [3]. In collaborative learning, the teacher / tutor / facilitator becomes a kind of score distributor who supports his musicians without playing himself. His role is essential for the coordination and harmonization of all participants, for collective and individual assessment,

provision of support, individual and group consultations, as well as for contributing to maintaining a friendly atmosphere, motivation, and the development of team spirit. By interacting, group members jointly contribute to the overall success [4]:

- giving and receiving support and assistance;
- exchanging information and resources;
- giving and receiving feedback;
- challenging the reasoning of others;
- intensifying efforts to achieve goals;
- sharing their achievements with each other;
- engaging in interpersonal relationships;
- caring about increasing the effectiveness of the group.

CONCLUSION

The influence of social interdependence on collaboration and interactivity in courses conducted on the basis of digital networks has been established. That is why we should emphasize the importance of interpersonal exchanges and informal socialization (e.g. in chat rooms) in order to achieve high quality learning outcomes in collaborative learning environments.

References:

1. Albéro B. Linard, M. & Robin J-Y. Petite fabrique de l'innovation à l'université. Paris: L'Harmattan, collection Logiques sociales, 2018.
2. Blandin B. Formateurs et formations multimédias. Paris: Édition d'Organisation, 2010.
3. Clarke J., Wideman R. & Eadie S. Apprenons ensemble: l'apprentissage coopératif en groupes restreints. Montréal: Les Éditions de la Chenelière, 2012.
4. Cohen E. G. Le travail de groupe: stratégies d'enseignement pour la classe hétérogène. Montréal: Les Éditions de la Chenelière, 2014.
5. Dasgupta S. Innovation in the Social Sciences: Herbert A. Simon and the birth of a research tradition. Dans L. V. Shavinina (dir.). The International Handbook on Innovation. Oxford: Elsevier, 2013, pp. 458–470.